

and Mar and is a major constraint to the early rice crop. We tested a new nursery-raising method and thereby identified a new rice pest.

Five recommended high yielding rices (see table) were sown in early Feb 1983. Seeds were sown in 1-m² plots and were covered with 1 cm layer of soil and 1 cm of cow dung compost. Covering the plots with a polythene sheet for 2 wk significantly raised the temperature (14-40° C vs outside temperatures of 4-

21° C). When the sheet was removed, we found a serious infestation of rice root aphid *Rhopalosiphum rufiabdominalis* (Sasaki). The nursery remained yellowish with stunted growth until the end of Feb, and circular dead spots called *aphid burns* developed. When we pulled the seedlings, we found that Ch-1093 was most susceptible (see table). Sprinkling the nursery with phosphamidon at 0.05% concentration effectively controlled the aphids.

When similar nurseries were grown on a raised trench (30 × 30 × 150 cm), *Rhopalosiphum maidis* (Fitch) became a pest. Other insects associated with this nursery technique were phytophagous beetle *Luperodes* sp. and predator beetles, *Micraspis inops* var. *vincta* (Gorham) and *Paederus* sp. A fungivorous and phoretic mite, *Uroovovella* sp., was also found in the root zone. *ℒ*

Movement of BPMC in rice

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Because downward movement of BPMC (2-Sec-butyl phenyl N-methyl carbamate) in rice has been reported, we quantified movement of BPMC from rice leaves to stems.

We conducted 2 greenhouse pot trials in 0.3 × 0.4 × 0.2 m³ trays. The upper leaves of 30- and 60-d-old TN1 plants were treated with 0.2% and 0.4% solutions of BPMC 50EC with an atomizer at constant volume basis while the lower 15 cm of stems was protected with a thermocole. Leaves and stems of all plants were sampled at 0, 1, 3, and 4 d after treatment. Thirty-day-old plants also were sampled after 5 and 6 d. Treatments were in a complete randomized block design with three replications. Foliage and stem samples

BPMC residues in rice leaves and stems, Bhopal, India.

Sampling interval (d)	BPMC residue ^a (ppm)							
	30-d crop				60-d crop			
	0.2% concentration		0.4% concentration		0.2% concentration		0.4% concentration	
	Foliage	Stem	Foliage	Stem	Foliage	Stem	Foliage	Stem
0	8.4	BDL	21.6	BDL	9.5	BDL	41.5	BDL
1	7.3	0.8	17.6	2.1	8.0	0.9	34.8	3.6
2	3.8	0.9	13.8	2.3	4.7	1.0	24.4	4.2
3	2.4	0.5	7.2	1.3	2.7	0.6	19.2	4.2
4	1.1	0.3	3.1	0.7	1.4	0.4	4.4	1.6
5	0.4	BDL	0.9	0.6	—	—	—	—
6	0.3	BDL	0.4	0.2	—	—	—	—

^a Av of 3 replications. BDL = below detectable level (less than 0.10 ppm).

were separately analyzed by spectrophotometrics.

On treatment day, BPMC deposits on leaves of 30-d plants treated with 0.2 and 0.4% solutions were 8.4 and 22 ppm. Corresponding values for 60-d plants were 9 and 41 ppm (see table). Residue on the leaves degraded gradually, persisting for 4-6 d. About 9% of the insecticide had moved to the

stem 24 h after treatment. BPMC concentration in stems increased to about 11% 2 d after treatment and then gradually decreased. The decrease may be due to dilution as a result of plant growth or may be because dissipation exceeded the downward movement of BPMC. Neither plant age nor dosage significantly affected downward movement. *ℒ*

Insect pests of upland rice in Uttar Pradesh

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Upland rice in Uttar Pradesh is attacked by green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant), brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal), leafroller *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenee), butterfly *Melanitis leda ismene*

(Cramer), rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thunberg) (*-varicornis* Fab.), stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), armyworm *Mythimna separata* (Walker), and aphid *Hysteroneura setariae* (Thomas). Of those, *N. virescens*, *L. varicornis*, *S. incertulas*, and *M. separata* are of major importance. In recent years, *M. separata* has become increasingly important, with severe infestations causing 60-80% yield losses. Losses to *L. acuta* are 15-20%, to *S. incertulas* 10-15%, and to *N. virescens* 5-10%. *ℒ*

Efficacy of three synthetic pyrethroids for caseworm control

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Caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* severely damages rice nurseries and young transplanted rice in thaladi (Nov-Dec) in Thanjavur district. Phosphamidon, monocrotophos, and endosulfan are recommended controls. We tested three synthetic pyrethroids for

Synthetic pyrethroids for caseworm control, Aduthurai, India, 1984.^a

Insecticide	Formulation (EC)	Dose (g ai/ha)	Damaged leaves before treatment (%)	Mortality ^b (%) after	
				24 h	48 h
Fenvalerate	20	100	81	97 a	91 a
	20	15	81	94 ab	94 a
Cypermethrin	25	80	80	95 a	91 a
	25	60	66	95 ab	94 a
Deltamethrin	2.8	15	82	94 ab	95 a
	2.8	11.25	90	91 ab	92 a
Endosulfan (standard check)	35	500	78	81 b	81 b
Untreated check			86	6 c	5 c

^aMean of 3 replications. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

caseworm control. IR50 was planted in 40 m².

Pretreatment caseworm damage was recorded on 12 randomly selected hills/plot. Damage between plots did not significantly differ. Results were recorded by counting live and dead larvae 24 and 48 h after treatment.

All pyrethroid treatments were superior to the control and the standard check (see table). Fenvalerate 20 EC sprayed at 100 g ai/ha gave 97% mortality at 24 and 48 h after treatment. *ℓ*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Survey of rodents and rodent damage in deep water rice

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We studied rodent activity in several deep water rice fields at Huntra Station, Ayutthaya Province, from Mar 1984 to Feb 1985. One hundred live traps baited with fresh fish were set on 3 consecutive nights at 4-6 wk intervals. In the same fields, stem damage caused by rodents was estimated several times. During the deepest flooding, a large, adjacent field also was sampled.

Rats *Bandicota indica*, *Rattus losea*, and *Rattus argentiventer* were active in the fields. Rat populations were influenced by food availability and floodwater level (see figure). At peak flooding, when all dikes were submerged, we trapped no *R. argentiventer*, but the other species remained active. *B. indica* and *R. losea* continued to live and reproduce in the field. Stem cutting by rats began in Jun and continued through stem elongation at 95 cm water depth. The cumulative seasonal damage probably exceeded 10% of the stems. *ℓ*

Species composition and numbers of rats, Huntra, Thailand, 1984-85. The dashed bars shown for Oct represent rat numbers in an adjacent farmer's field.

Soil and Crop Management

Nitrogen fertilizer efficiency in two major rice soils of Bangladesh

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We evaluated N fertilizer efficiency in

Grey Floodplain (Mymensingh) and Red Brown Terrace (Madhupur) soils in Bangladesh in boro, aus, and transplanted aman. BR-3 was planted at both sites. Soil at Mymensingh was a silt loam with pH 6.8, 0.57% organic C, CEC and exchangeable K 9.2 and 0.25